

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th December 2022

Accepted: 18th December 2022

Online: 19th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Cluster, unified system, territory, national economy, organization, production.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SINGLE COMPLEX CLUSTER SYSTEM IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN

Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich

Namangan Engineering and Technological Institute, DSc., Associate

Professor of the Department of Economics, Uzbekistan. Email:

bustonov1975@mail.ru.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7456189>

ABSTRACT

The article describes the economic evaluation of the factors affecting the organization and management of the single complex system of regional clusters, as well as theoretical and methodological approaches in the direction of assessing the level of competitiveness of the integration processes in clusters based on the sectoral approach.

INTRODUCTION.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is being paid to the modernization of the national economy and the establishment and development of clusters based on market principles.

A cluster associated with an innovative approach to economic management is a modern management mechanism that serves to increase the competitiveness of individual regions, sectors and/or countries. Today, many examples can be given that determine the high socio-economic importance of clusters in many industrialized countries.

There is an opportunity to realize the strategic goals of the state regarding the formation and development of the innovative economy in the operating clusters. The formation and development of a single comprehensive system of regional clusters by the state will serve as an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of the national economy in the future.

The goal of forming and developing a single complex system of regional clusters is to attract many new techniques and technologies to production or service, to create a developed economic space and ensure its rapid development.

To develop regions and create jobs, to increase the contribution of a single complex system of regional clusters in increasing the income of the population, to establish close cooperative relations between the participants of these regions, based on the principles of project management, using complex cluster approaches widely, to create competitive finished products and components using local raw materials and materials. creating the most favorable conditions for attracting foreign investments, first of all, foreign direct investments, for the establishment of high-tech modern enterprises for the localization of production of goods and for the organization of modern innovative productions with advanced technology

with the participation of leading foreign companies and corporations.

The attractiveness of the single complex system of regional clusters and the need to develop criteria for its assessment, as well as researching its theoretical and practical foundations, are of great importance.

In the conditions of establishing a new Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the organization of their activities in the form of clusters in the development of industry, food, fisheries and agriculture based on modern requirements. Thanks to the opportunities created in recent years, new enterprises are emerging, entrepreneurs are developing freely, and the level of processing is increasing. In this regard, scientific research in the directions of improving the economic and legal basis of the operation of the single complex system of regional clusters, increasing the efficiency of crediting the activity of clusters, continuously organizing production and improving the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of activity, taking into account financial stability, and improving approaches to forecasting the activity of clusters based on the effective use of production factors. It is desirable to expand research.

Худудий кластерларнинг ягона комплекс тизимининг фаолиятининг ривожлантиришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш бўйича илмий таклиф ва амалий тавсиялар ишлаб чиқиш зарурати туғилмоқда, яъни:

- formation of innovative clusters in the regions (ie Mingbuloq district) in horticulture, cotton-textile, food, light industry, fishing, construction, agriculture

and clarification of the theoretical bases of research of vertical integration processes;

- improving the methodology of vertical integration processes and structures of the single complex system of regional clusters based on econometric models;

- Specialization of economic entities, horticulture, fishing, construction, light industry, food, agriculture areas and analysis of economic efficiency of product cultivation in Mingbuloq district;

- development of a system of indicative indicators of the activity of a single complex system of territorial clusters and their evaluation criteria;

- to study the legal bases of the single complex system of regional clusters, to identify and eliminate legal obstacles to development;

- development of a legal-normative document on the formation and development of the single complex system of territorial clusters;

- assessment of the factors affecting the organization and management of the single complex system of regional clusters and the competitiveness of integration processes in clusters based on a branch approach;

- To identify problems related to the improvement of the organizational and economic mechanisms of the formation and development of a unified complex system of regional clusters in Uzbekistan and to develop scientific and practical proposals aimed at solving them;

- development of proposals and recommendations on improving the state's support mechanisms for the development of the single complex system of territorial clusters;

- to develop a scientific proposal and practical recommendations in the direction

of improving the organizational-economic and management mechanisms of the single complex system of regional clusters.

Economic assessment of the factors affecting the organization and management of the single complex system of regional clusters and integration processes in clusters on the basis of the sectoral approach is explained by the fact that it can be used as an important source in the development of theoretical and methodological approaches in the direction of assessing the level of competitiveness and in the implementation of scientific research on the topic.

There are two main categories of clusters, formed along the spatial and functional axes. Spatial groupings of similar and related companies and industries are referred to as regional clusters. Functionally connected systems, less limited by strictly defined regions, belong to industrial clusters. Clusters can have different sizes and shapes depending on their depth and complexity.

Formation of clusters, development of existing and creation of new territorial production complexes based on the use of the effect of placement, concentration, combination and cooperation (Fig. 1).

One example of the process of creating clusters is the experience of the Japanese economy, first based on the development of a system of subcontracting and subcontracting links between a number of large and a network of small enterprises. A typical large Japanese cluster consists of a single, relatively large parent enterprise, using the services of two or three levels of subcontracting firms, usually located in geographical proximity to it. Instead of vertical integration, independent subcontractors of the first level are connected with the parent company by long-term contracts.

This largely eliminates the potential competition inherent in the free market, but purely price considerations in the procurement of components contribute to the optimization of production. Clustering processes can also be observed in various developing countries such as India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Mexico and others. There are more than 2,000 clusters in India, of which 388 are industrial and 1,657 are handicraft enterprises. The clusters supply more than 60% of India's exports, and some large clusters produce up to 90% of the country's selected products (clothing, jewelry and leather goods).

Fig. 1. Model of the formation of unified territorial-production clusters¹

One example of the process of creating clusters is the experience of the Japanese economy, first based on the development of a system of subcontracting and subcontracting links between a number of large and a network of small enterprises. A typical large Japanese cluster consists of a single, relatively large parent enterprise, using the services of two or three levels of subcontracting firms, usually located in geographical proximity to it. Instead of vertical integration, independent subcontractors of the first level are connected with the parent company by long-term contracts.

This largely eliminates the potential competition inherent in the free market, but purely price considerations in the procurement of components contribute to the optimization of production. Clustering processes can also be observed in various developing countries such as India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Mexico and others. There are more than 2,000 clusters in India, of which 388 are industrial and 1,657 are handicraft enterprises. The clusters supply more than 60% of India's exports, and some large clusters produce up to 90% of the country's selected products (clothing, jewelry and leather goods).

The practice of formation and functioning of cluster systems allows us to identify the necessary conditions for their effective functioning:

– the presence of a large leading enterprise that determines the long-term economic, innovative and other strategy of the entire

cluster, and in many cases the basing region as a whole;

– specialization, which involves the interconnection of cluster members through the main activity, providing an emphasis on the same market or production process;

– regional localization of the bulk of economic entities – enterprises participating in the cluster system;

– plurality of actors: the cluster implies diversity and lack of monostructure;

– the stability of economic ties of economic entities – participants in the cluster system, the dominant value of these ties for the majority of participants;

– long-term coordination of interaction between the participants of the system within the framework of its production programs, innovative processes of the main management systems, quality control, etc.;

– orientation of products, as a rule, towards export or import substitution (the focus on creating competitive products that can be exported abroad or at least outside the region is a characteristic feature of cluster systems);

– innovativeness – the widest possible use of scientific achievements, openness to new ideas on the part of the management of the participating enterprises, effective use of intellectual capital, intangible innovative assets, venture capital.

Regarding the regions of Uzbekistan, there are a number of conditions that both contribute to and negatively affect the formation of clusters. Positive conditions, of course, include: the existence of technological and scientific infrastructure; psychological readiness for cooperation, based on historically established production and economic ties. Among the negative factors are the low quality of the

¹ Developed by the author

business climate and the level of development of associative structures that do not cope with the task of developing priorities in the development of the regional economy; a short-term planning horizon is widely used, while in the case of cluster management, the real benefits of

cluster development appear only after 3-5 years.

The main criterion for the efficiency of cluster development can be the maximization of GRP production per capita with the maximum use of available factors of production.

Fig.2. Sustainable regional development based on the formation of regional clusters of enterprises²

At the same time, the degree of concentration of production within the cluster must correspond to the size of production and the productivity of the factors of production used, since excessive concentration is as undesirable as insufficient concentration.

In addition, for the successful implementation of the strategic development priorities identified by the state, continuous further monitoring and evaluation of the clusters that have developed in the region in the following areas is necessary:

- analysis of changes in profits received by cluster enterprises;
- change in the share of the cluster in the volume of regional production;
- change in the share of the cluster in the trade turnover of the region;
- change in the growth of exports of products produced by the cluster, compared with the growth in exports of the entire national economy.

Evaluation of the cluster activity according to the above parameters will make it possible to make timely adjustments to the program for increasing the competitiveness of the regional economy, to mobilize the necessary resources for the further development of clusters in the country.

For the economy of the region and a single territory, clusters play the role of growth points for the domestic market. Following the first, new clusters and the stability of regional development are most often formed, the competitiveness of the region

as a whole increases. Long value-added production chains increase investments in the region and related tax revenues, lead to the diversification of the regional economy, solve employment problems and create new jobs, and are a tool for interacting with the business community.

With the help of clusters, public authorities and administrations can more effectively use new, market, trends for the socio-economic development of the region. Clusters provide authorities with a toolkit for effective interaction with business, allow them to better understand its characteristic indicators and tactical tasks, to purposefully, realistically and motivatedly carry out strategic planning of regional resources and development of territories. Therefore, the formation of a cluster system for organizing the development of territorial-production complexes of the regions of Uzbekistan seems to be an effective mechanism for ensuring sustainable regional development.

² Compiled by the author

References:

1. Bustonov M.M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth// European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260 2020.Vol 07, Issue 07. <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?sort=count-f&src> (SCOPUS).
2. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality// Test Engineering & Management. 2019. November-December. <http://www.testmagzine.biz/index.php/testmagzine/article/view/221>
3. Bustonov M.M. The Firm Aspects and conditions Providing the Qualities of Economic Growth in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017, 4(4): 32-39 <http://www.aascit.org/journal/archive2?journalId=918&paperId=4704>
4. Bustonov M.M., Ensuring Long-Term Economic Growth in the World and Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Extensive, Intensive and Digital Economy. Miasto Przyszłości Kielce 2022, ISSN-L: 2544-980X. <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/406>
5. Bustonov M.M., Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal (MRJ) Volume: 01 Issue: 03 | 2022 ISSN: (2751-7543) <http://innosci.org/index.php/wos/article/view/53/37>
6. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
7. Bustonov M.M. The firm aspects and conditions providing the qualities of economic growth in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017/ <http://www.aascit.org/journal/Ijeta>
8. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality. // Test engineering & Management November-December 2019.
9. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
10. Ishimbaev R.N. Competitiveness of small business. Science and innovation. International scientific journal volume 1 ISSUE 8 | ISSN: 2181-3337 p 90-96
11. 15. Ishimbaev R.N. Criteria and principle of capability. Miasta Przyslosci. Vol. 29 (2022) November P 334-337.